

Energy Dissipation Studies of Mg Based Nanocomposites Using an Innovative Circle-fit approach

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Abstract

In the present study, energy dissipation capability of magnesium containing variable amounts of nano-size alumina particle is investigated. Synthesis of materials was accomplished using a solidification processing route. Energy dissipation in the form of damping capacity was determined using free-free type suspended beam arrangement coupled with circle-fit approach. This technique is based on classical vibration theory, by which the geometry and material properties of the metal matrix composites are related to resonant frequency and structural damping of the test specimen. Using the fact that the ratio of the vibration response to the applied force fits to a circle in the Argand plane for each resonant frequency of the test specimen, the damping factor and natural frequency is predicted accurately for the test specimen. The results revealed that an increase in the alumina content upto 1.134% volume percentage lead to an increase in the damping capacity upto 64%. Attempt is made to correlate the increase in damping with the increased volume fraction of nanosize alumina particle in the composite samples.

Keywords A. Nanomaterial, B. Plastic zone, C. Interface, D. Anelasticity, E. Non-destructive testing.

Introduction

Nanostructured materials (microstructural dimensions less than 100-nm) have thrilled the material community due to their unconventional behavior in terms of mechanical, physical and chemical properties compared to their coarse-grain sized counterparts [1-2]. It is well known that higher damping property results in faster energy dissipation and this is required in a variety of applications, such as, spacecrafts, semiconductor equipments, robotics, etc. Among the vast range of materials available for design of dynamic mechanical systems, high dynamic stiffness with better damping characteristics of metal matrix composites (MMC) makes them an attractive choice during selection. Magnesium is one such material that has the capability to exhibit such properties especially when it is unified with ceramic particulates such as SiC and Al₂O₃ [3-6]. Now with the advent of the nanotechnology of producing fine reinforcement particles, the art of nanocomposites has taken shape.

Based on the works of several researchers, both intrinsic and extrinsic mechanisms contributes to the overall damping capability of MMC through point defect relaxation, dislocation motion, grain boundary sliding, coulomb friction at the matrix-reinforcement interface, thermoelastic effects, etc [5, 7, 8]. During cooling of the MMCs, mismatch in coefficient of thermal expansion of the reinforcement and matrix results in interfacial stresses, which results in the generation of dislocation in the matrix material [9]. Mechanical spectroscopic studies have shown relaxation damping peak results due to dislocation motion [5, 7]. Among the various extrinsic damping

mechanisms thermoelastic damping is one of the primary mechanism, caused due to thermal currents within the material due to heating in the compressively stress zone and cooling at the tensile stress zone. Damping studies of Kinra et al. on continuous and particulate type metal matrix composites have shown that the thermoelastic damping corresponds to the lowest bound for the total damping capability of the composite [5]. Thus a particulate type composite can be well tailored for enhanced damping and stiffness characteristics.

In this paper, effect of variation in weight percentage of the nano-size alumina (Al_2O_3) particulate on the damping characteristics of magnesium metal matrix is taken for detailed study. The stiffness and damping characteristics corresponding to different MMC composition was measured from the frequency characteristics of extruded rod specimens obtained from impact-based measurement. The loss factor corresponding to the internal friction was calculated using a circle-fit approach, which eliminates any error from specimen geometry and support structure.

Table 1 Results of density, CTE and hardness measurement of Mg and Mg/ Al_2O_3 composites.

Wt. % of Al_2O_3	Vol. % of Al_2O_3	Density (gm/cm^3)	CTE ($\times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	Microhardness (HV)
-	0.000	1.7397	28.4 ± 0.3	40 ± 0
0.5	0.224	1.7523	27.5 ± 0.1	51 ± 1
1.5	0.677	1.7470	ND*	56 ± 1
2.5	1.134	1.7623	25.1 ± 0.3	66 ± 1

* ND: Not Determined.

Experimental Procedures

Materials and Processes

Disintegrated Melt Deposition (DMD) technique [6] was used to synthesize cast magnesium (99.9% pure) reinforced with 0.5, 1.5 and 2.5-weight percentages of 50-nm sized Al_2O_3 particulates. The technique involves melting and superheating the magnesium turnings with reinforcement particulates to 750°C under inert Ar gas atmosphere in a graphite crucible. Superheated slurry was stirred at 460rpm for 2.5 minutes using a zirtex coated twin blade (pitch 450°) stirrer to facilitate the incorporation and uniform distribution of reinforcement particulates in the metallic melt. The melt was then released from the crucible and disintegrated by two jets of argon gas, orientated normal to the melt stream, and subsequently deposited onto a metallic substrate. The synthesis of monolithic magnesium was carried out using similar steps except that no reinforcement particulates were added. The resulting ingots were subsequently hot extruded at 250°C employing an extrusion ratio of 20.25:1.

The results of the density measurements of the MMC specimens obtained using Archimedes' principle [4] are listed in Table 1. The coefficient of thermal expansion of the monolithic sample was determined on extruded samples using thermal-mechanical analyzer and the Vickers hardness (HV) was obtained using a digital micro-hardness tester (Matsuzawa model MXT50) [4]. Table 1 lists the experimentally determined values of hardness and coefficient of thermal expansion for the monolithic and the composite samples.

Fig. 1 Typical circle fit plot of: (a) pure mg (b) Mg/ 0.5 wt.% Al₂O₃ (c) Mg/ 1.5 wt.% Al₂O₃ (d) Mg/ 2.5 wt.% Al₂O₃.

Damping Measurement Method

The impact-based “Free-Free” or “Suspended” beam method was performed based on the ASTM C1259-98 standard [10]. Description of the experimental setup is described in reference [6]. The receptance frequency response function (FRF) ‘ $\alpha(\omega)$ ’, which is the ratio between displacement response to the applied impact force, was plotted as a nyquist plot corresponding to the resonance condition [6]. Using least square technique a circle was fit and based on hysterically damped vibrating system the circle diameter can be shown to be inversely dependent on the damping coefficient. Fig. 1 shows typical circle fit plots of the monolithic and the composite samples. The exact location and determination of the natural frequency and the corresponding damping factor ‘ η_{free} ’ was calculated using frequency spacing technique [6]. Fig. 2 shows are typical circle plot from which two points are selected for damping loss factor calculation, denoted as point a and b corresponding to frequencies ω_a and ω_b , respectively, which are lesser and greater than the

magnesium was found to be 0.011, which can be favourably compared with the damping measurements of Lazan [11] on cast magnesium (99% pure) at 60 Hz, which is around 0.014 under low strain amplitude.

The average sizes of alumina particulates was 50-nm. In general, uniform distribution of alumina particulates was observed and was confirmed based on the isotropic material behavior observed in terms of the elastic modulus in all the composite samples, from a global perspective.

Fig. 3 Decay of vibration amplitude with time under different damping loss factor in a cantilever when subjected to a unit starting deformation.

Table 2 lists the experimentally determined loss factor variation with an increase in weight percentage of Al_2O_3 in the magnesium matrix. Fig. 3 explains such an increase in damping loss factor help in achieving faster settling of the vibration in a structural system such as a beam with cantilever like support system (e.g. a satellite's antenna structure) and subjected to a initial unit deformation followed by free oscillations. It may be noted that the increase in damping of Mg is realised as a result of presence and increasing weight percentage of Al_2O_3 irrespective of the fact that Al_2O_3 has lower loss factor of the order of 0.0009 [12] as compared to magnesium, which has loss factor of the order of 0.011. Such an increase in the loss factor due to the addition of Al_2O_3 can be attributed to the Al_2O_3 associated intrinsic and extrinsic damping mechanisms as described in the forthcoming paragraphs.

In addition, from Table 2 it can be observed that the elastic modulus of the composite increases with addition of the alumina particulates. This is consistent with the trend exhibited by magnesium based metal matrix composites [3]. Thus a good interface between the alumina and magnesium matrix can be expected to exist in all the composite samples. It is interesting to note that for both good and bad interfacial bonding condition between the ceramic particle and the metal matrix, the overall damping characteristics increases in a MMC due to different damping mechanisms. In the present study, a semi-coherent or incoherent interface can be expected to exist due to a ceramic-metal type interface at the atomistic level [13]. Thus in the present study, the increased damping can be seen as a result of the presence of plastic zone, increase in dislocation density and due to other damping sources such as elasto-thermodynamic damping and grain boundary sliding mechanisms which would be critically analyzed for its validity in the following paragraphs.

In particulate reinforced MMCs (PRMMCs) inclusion of the hard ceramic particulates causes high residual stresses around the particulates in the form of an annular plastic zone due to large difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion of magnesium and silicon carbide, which are responsible for the generation of plastic zone at the particulate/matrix interface. The CTE for Al₂O₃ is 9 ppm/°C [5] and for Mg is 28.4 ppm/°C from the present study (refer Table 1). Based on the works of Dunand and Mortensen [14], the size of the plastic zone C_s can be estimated as:

$$C_s = r_s \left(\frac{\Delta\alpha E \Delta T}{(1-\nu)\sigma_y} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta\alpha$ is the difference between the CTEs of Mg and Al₂O₃, ΔT is the temperature difference which is around 227°C, E and ν are the matrix elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio, σ_y is the matrix yield stress and r_s is the particulate radius. Thus for the present experiment samples containing 50-nm size Al₂O₃ particulates, the plastic zone radius is calculated using equation (4) and the corresponding volume fraction is listed in Table 2. Recently based on mechanical spectroscopic studies, Carreno-Morelli, Urreta and Schaller [15] proposed a simplistic model to determine the damping due to plastic zone as follows:

$$\tan \phi \approx \frac{f_{zp} G_c \int \sigma d\varepsilon}{\pi \sigma_0^2} \quad (5)$$

where f_{zp} is the plastic zone volume fraction, G_c is the shear modulus of the composite sample, σ_0 is the alternating shear stress amplitude, ε is the corresponding strain, acting on the specimen. Thus it is clear from equation (5) that the damping depends directly on the volume fraction of the plastic zone and the strain amplitude. Also it is clear that the overlapping of plastic zones can occur for situations when the plastic zone is larger with smaller inter-particulate distance which is possible as the weight percentage increases. Table 2 lists the predicted inter-particulate distance for the experiment samples based on the model of Nardone and Prewo [16] described as follows:

$$\lambda = \left[\frac{lt}{V_f} \right]^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where λ is the inter-particulate spacing, t , l and V_f are the thickness, length and volume fraction of the Al₂O₃ particulate, respectively. Thus presence of clusters can be expected to change the plastic zones and thereby influence the overall damping capacity. The increase in the presence of plastic zones in the composite samples due to the presence of reinforcement can be seen as an increase in hardness of the composite samples listed in Table 1, which is found to increase steadily with the reinforcement volume fraction, compared to the monolithic sample.

Another contributing damping mechanism arises due to an increase in dislocation density in the metallic matrix due to the presence of the hard and brittle reinforcing particulates. These dislocations are generated due to thermal mismatch strain caused due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion values between the metal matrix and hard brittle reinforcing phase. As mentioned previously, the CTE difference between Al₂O₃ and Mg is around 19.4 ppm/°C from the present study. Thus the dislocation density generated can be quite significant at the interface and can be predicted using the model based on prismatic punching of dislocations at a ceramic particulate [17]. Thus it can be shown in the form of equation (7) that the dislocation density ρ depends on the thermal mismatch strain, ε , (the product of temperature change, ΔT , during solidification of MMCs and CTE difference, $\Delta\alpha$, between reinforcement and matrix), the volume fraction of the ceramic reinforcement, f , the Burgers vector, b , the particulate size, t , and

$$\rho = \frac{6 B \varepsilon V_f}{bt(1-V_f)} \quad (7)$$

the particulate aspect ratio, s . B is a geometric constant that depends on the aspect ratio (it varies between 12 for equiaxed particulate and 4 for whisker-like particulate) [17]. For Mg- Al_2O_3 , the thermal mismatch strain during cooling is found to be typically 0.43% during cooling from 250°C to room temperature. Based on equation (7) the dislocation density for the different experiment samples was calculated and are listed in Table 2 and with an assumption of 0.3-nm for the burgers vector [18].

Granato-Lucke mechanism is a well-accepted theory that explains the damping mechanism by dislocations [19]. When a dislocation is pinned by two obstacles such as the impurity atoms, ceramic particulates or antiplane dislocations, it behaves like an elastic vibrating string. Under low amplitude of the applied cyclic load the string vibrates to dissipate energy. Thus at low strain amplitude the damping is independent of the strain amplitude and is dependent only on the frequency while at high strain amplitude the damping nature increases tremendously due to breakaway of the dislocations from their pinned positions due to excessive bowing [19, 20].

In the present experimental setup, the strain amplitude induced in the specimen is of the order of 10^{-6} at which the dislocation-based damping is mainly due to frequency dependent part and is expressed as follows:

$$Q_f^{-1} \approx \frac{a_o B A L^4 \omega^2}{\pi^2 C b^2} \quad (8)$$

where a_o is a numerical factor of order 1, B is the damping constant, ω is the operating frequency, L is the effective dislocation loop length which depends on the pinning distance, C is the dislocation line tension ($\approx 0.5Gb^2$), G is the shear modulus, b is burgers vector and Λ is the total dislocation density. This shows that the damping depends on the dislocation density, frequency of cyclic stress and burgers vector b of the bulk material [20, 21]. Thus increased density of dislocation due to presence of Al_2O_3 particulates in the magnesium matrix contributes towards increased dislocation-based damping characteristics in the MMC. It may also be noted that the dislocation density increases with Al_2O_3 weight percentage (equation (7)) and thus an increase in damping of the magnesium matrix was expected due to increase in Al_2O_3 weight percentage. The experimental results listed in Table 2 conform to this hypothesis.

In addition, damping studies of Zhang, Gungor and Lavernia [22] shows that the presence of voids in the metallic matrix also provides additional damping to the composite. Presently research work is in progress to validate the presence of micropores in these nanocomposites using high-resolution electron microscope. Other damping mechanisms such as grain boundary sliding [23] and elasto-thermodynamic damping [24-26] can be seen to be insignificant in the present experimental study due to room temperature operation conditions, sample dimensions and frequency magnitude.

The increase in the elastic modulus with increase in weight percentage of reinforcement can be attributed to the higher elastic modulus of Al_2O_3 , which is reported to be about 420 GPa [5] as compared to the monolithic Mg sample's elastic modulus value of 42.77 GPa, based on the present study (see Table 2). In addition, any presence of brittle oxide phases of magnesium in the metallic matrix are also expected to increase the overall composite's stiffness, due to their higher stiffness compared to the parent materials. In a previous study [27] the authors have used various theoretical models such as the Shear Lag model, Halpin-Tsai model and the Eshelby model to explain such an increase in the MMC's stiffness with reinforcement.

The results of the present study, in essence, reveal that the circle-fit approach when combined with the impact-based measurement of the suspended beam is capable of measuring damping loss factor and elastic modulus of the metal based nanocomposites. Thus from the above discussions,

it is encouraging to note that addition of hard nano-size alumina particulates in the metallic matrix increases damping significantly. Presently, further work is in progress on other composite formulations to further strengthen the feasibility of this approach. Nevertheless, the testing methodology introduced in this study provides the researchers with yet another tool for measuring the damping behavior of nanomaterials.

Conclusions

1. The free-free beam type flexural resonance method can be successfully used with circle-fit approach to measure the damping characteristics of the magnesium containing different volume fraction of nano-size alumina particulates.
2. The hardness, elastic modulus and damping capacity of the pure magnesium matrix increased as a result of the increasing presence of Al_2O_3 particulates.
3. An increase in damping with an increase in the weight/volume percentage of Al_2O_3 particulates can be attributed to a progressive increase in the energy dissipation due to simultaneous influence of various intrinsic and extrinsic damping mechanisms.

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